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THE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON READING HABITS

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to conduct a quantitative inquiry to understand the effects of social media on the reading habits of the students in Government Degree college for women M.A Road Srinagar. A well designed and structured questionnaire was used to collect data. Out of 120 questionnaires, 105 questionnaires were analysed. The results reveal that most of the students from the Journalism department use social media during college hours in order to keep themselves updated with news. The study also revealed that Journalism students use "WhatsApp" more frequently than other social media applications during college hours. Moreover, the majority of the students agreed that there is a negative impact of social media on reading habits. The study demonstrated that 100% of students from the Journalism department use at least one form of social media during college hours. The findings also revealed that only **one out of hundred** students use the library on a daily basis.

KEYWORDS

Social media, reading habits, Journalism students.

INTRODUCTION

Social media is defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundation of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content" (**Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010, p. 61**). Social media is widely used throughout the globe for sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through virtual networks. Social media includes computer-based applications in which content is shared to inform, entertain, or guide the people in an effective way. More than 3.8 billion people use social media around the world. According to (**Boyd and Ellison, 2007**), "The social networking sites have transformed the thought of global village into a reality where billions of people communicate through social networking sites". Social media is an ever-changing and ever-evolving field. Every minute a new trend emerges which is followed by millions of social media users. Social media has different features from creating content in the form of photography, videography, writing blogs, audio sharing, posting comments and engaging the audience through new trends. According to the Pew Research Center, nearly 90% of people between the age group of 18 and 29 used at least one form of social media. Social media is popular among young people, particularly students. Using social media has both positive as well as negative effects on reading habits of students.

Reading is an exercise for the mind. It helps to develop communicative skills and also develops cognitive abilities. It not only provides knowledge about the world but also helps to learn about different cultures, societies and traditions. According to **Dadzie (2008)**, "Reading is the ability to understand words contained in a document and make use of the knowledge for personal growth and development". In **Adu-Sarkodee, Asante, and Akussah (2015) words**, "Reading is making meaning out of recorded information printed by an individual". "Reading is a process of thinking, recalling and relating concepts under the functioning of written words" (**Du Toit, 2007**). Reading and learning is important for the progress of any society.

Reading habits play a crucial role in the scholarly output of the students (**Cunningham and Stanovovich, 1998**). If students possess good reading habits, they can increase their critical reasoning skills and ultimately have better academic outcomes. Besides, even the reading of non-academic books enhances students' language skills (**Balan, Katenga, and Simon, 2019**). Specifically, the study will examine types of social media being used by students during college hours and some of the reasons why they use it in the first place; how it affects their reading habits; how much time they spend on social media during college hours and establish the relationship between social media usage, and their reading habits.

Literature Review

Social media, derived from the social software movement, are a collection of Internet websites, services, and practices that support collaboration, community building, participation, and sharing (Junco et al. 2010). Bryer and Zavatarro (2001), define social media as 'technologies that facilitate social interaction, make possible collaboration, and enable deliberation across stakeholders. These technologies include blogs, wikis, media (audio, photo, video, text) sharing tools, networking platforms, and virtual worlds (Bryer and Zavatarro, 2001).

Social media according to Mozee (2012) is a term commonly used to describe different types of communication platforms and electronic ways of interacting. It is further described as a collection of Internet Based applications that build on the ideological and technological underpinnings of Web 2.0 and permits the formulation and exchange of user-generated content and depend mostly on mobile and Web technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, create, discuss and modify user-generated content (Kaplan and Haenlein 2010). Ezeah et al. (2013) describe social media as a modern interactive communication channel through which people connect to one another, share ideas, experiences, pictures, messages and information of common interest. Bryer and Zavatarro (2011) viewed it as technologies that facilitate social interaction, make possible collaboration, and enable deliberations across stakeholders. Others also describe it as a group of internet-based applications that allows the creation and exchange of users' generated content (Anjugu 2013).

As Dadzie (2008) puts it, reading is the technique of understanding words contained in a text. They make use of the knowledge for personal growth and development. This suggests making meaning out of recorded information either printed or non-printed. Individuals read for different reasons and purposes, some of which include for pleasure, leisure, relaxation, information and for knowledge. Reading is an individual's ability to identify symbols and the connection of suitable meaning to them. It needs identification

and comprehension. Comprehension abilities assist the student in comprehending the meaning of words in isolation and in context (Palani, 2012). Indeed, reading books is the most suitable medium through which knowledge is transmitted from generation to generation (Issa et al., 2012). As Gallo (2007) pointed out, reading books yield their best to the individual if they read them at the time at which a particular masterpiece may ideally be chewed and digested. Consequently, reading activities in which students engage may considerably influence their studying skills and academic performance. There is a general sense in which an individual appreciates the connection between excellent reading culture and the academic achievement of students generally, (Issa et al., 2012). As Shabo and Usofia (2009) pointed out, the reading culture of learners has been washed down the drain as a consequence of the evolution of technology and advent of social media.

Research Questions

The study addresses the following research question:

1. What are the reasons for using social media during college hours among the students?
2. What are the patterns of reading habits among the students?
3. How do students perceive the impact of social media on reading habits?
4. How often do students make use of college libraries?
5. Do students prefer social media over reading or vice-versa?
6. How much time students spend on social media during college hours?

METHODOLOGY

The study opted for quantitative research design, and a questionnaire-based survey method was used to collect data. The choice of research design has opted for the basis of the methodological dimensions of the already conducted research on similar topics in which a structured questionnaire was used to study the phenomenon.

The population of this study consisted of 120 students from the department of Journalism and Mass Communication of Government Women's College M.A Road, Srinagar.

Government Women's College is an oldest college which includes 9 departments. Although it was tough to study the students from all the departments, the Department of Journalism and Mass Communication was selected as per their syllabus requirement which is to analyse different newspapers, magazines and books and an assumption was made about their tendency to write more, than other departments of the college.

To gain a representative sample, cluster sampling method was adopted. The entire student population of Journalism department was considered as the target population of the study. The college has a total of nine (9) academic departments out of which one (1) was selected. From the selected department, the study was conducted in all the semesters separately. In the end a total of 120 questionnaires were handed over to students for their responses. About 120 questionnaires were distributed to students of the Journalism Department and a total of 105 representing approximately 88% of the questionnaires were retrieved. a comprehensive survey questionnaire was designed to attain the research objectives. The questionnaire was self-constructed after extensive consideration of related literature to ensure that relevant items were included. The closed-ended questions were intended to

collect data that would facilitate accurate analysis. However, some open ended questions were asked in order to specify the cause of the issue.

Demographic Information:

The demographic information includes the ratio of male and female respondents. The age group of the respondents was almost the same.

Gender	n	%
Male	63	60
Female	42	40
Total	105	100.0

Findings and Discussions

Table 1: Types of social media sites mostly used by students during college hours

Media	n	%
Instagram	24	22.9
Snapchat	24	22.9
Whatsapp	39	37.1
Others	18	17.1
Total	105	100.0

From Table 1 it could be observed that out of 105 respondents 39 representing about 37% of the students stated the social media site they mostly use is WhatsApp. Meanwhile, 24 (22.9%) of the students resort to Instagram and Snapchat as the social media site they visit. From the trend of the responses it can be concluded that WhatsApp, Instagram and Snapchat are the Social Media(SM) sites mostly accessed by students.

Table 2: Reasons students use social media during college hours

Reasons	n	%
To be up to date with current news and events	48	45.7
Boredom during college hours	27	25.7

Do not use social media	15	14.3
Others	15	14.3
Total	105	100.0

The students surveyed were asked to indicate the reasons for which they use the social media sites during college hours. Summary of responses as shown in Table 2 gives the impression that (n=48, 45.7%) of the respondents stated they use SM to stay up to date with current news and events. Additionally, 27 (about 26.%) of the respondents also noted that they use SM only because they get bored during college hours.

Table 3: Use of college libraries by students

In Table 3, the respondents were asked about how often they make use of college libraries. The results show that only 1% of the students use college libraries on a daily basis. However, 80% of the respondents stated that they either use the library on a monthly basis or they never visit the library. Additionally, (n=21, 20% of the respondents noted that they make use of college libraries on a weekly basis.

Time/Frequency	n	%
Daily	1	1
Weekly	21	20
Monthly	42	40
Never	41	39
Total	105	100.0

Table 4: Average time spent accessing SM sites

Table 4 presents a summary of responses concerning the average time respondents spend on SM sites. The responses reflect the position that more than half of the respondents (n=60, 57.1 %), access social media for 1 hour. The results also show that (n=21, 20 %) of the respondents did not have access to social media. However, (n=9, 8.6 %) respondents use social media for more than 2 hours.

Time	n	%
0 hrs	21	20
1 hrs	60	57.1
2 hrs	15	14.3
More than 2 hrs	9	8.6
Total	105	100.0

Table 5: Impacts of social media on reading habits

In Figure 1, respondents were requested to indicate if there is an impact of social media on their reading habits. Summary of responses as shown in Figure 1 reveals that the majority (85.7%) of the respondents indicated that there is an impact of SM on their reading habits, while as 5.7% of the respondents indicated that SM does not impact their reading habits. However, 8.6% of the respondents did not know if social media is affecting their reading habits.

SM impact on Reading habits:

Figure 1: Impact of SM on Reading habits

Conclusion and recommendations

Schill (2011) believes that the more time students spend on social media, the less time they spend reading. Since social media has become a vital component of the daily life of students, particularly Journalism students, the study, accordingly, concludes that social media should be used reasonably to obtain information. Though most of the students use

social media for obtaining information however a good percentage of students did not make a positive use of social media. Some students argue that social media has worsened their reading habits as well as their health. Therefore, time spent on social media must also be reduced by students. Journalism students must make use of college libraries since it will consequently enhance their communication skills as well as general academic performance. The study consequently recommends that Government Women's College Srinagar should conduct workshops to spread awareness about the excessive use of social media and its serious threats to the health of the students. Furthermore, the authority should also organise programmes to encourage the students to use libraries. The study also recommends that there should be monthly competitions about general knowledge of the students which will in turn encourage the students to develop reading habits.

References

<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234641415.pdf>

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Dr-Arif/publication/338658981_The_Effects_of_Social_Media_on_Reading_Habits/links/5e58e9434585152ce8f518d4/The-Effects-of-Social-Media-on-Reading-Habits.pdf?origin=publication_detail
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XiKWSovORW33KVVjRgYda2Tf56EZeWBaFFcfZQ_HU4I/edit

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=9499&context=libphilprac>

<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-media.asp>

Palani, K. K. (2012). Promoting reading habits and creating literate society. *Researchers World*, 3(2), 90.

Balan, S., Katenga, J. E., & Simon, A. (2019). Reading Habits and Their Influence on Academic Achievement among Students at Asia Pacific International University. In *Abstract Proceedings International Scholars Conference* (Vol. 7, No. 1, pp. 1490-1516).

Kaplan A. M. and Haenlin M. (2010) Users of t

Schill, R (2011). Social Networking Teens Mare Likely to Drink Use Drugs. Retrieved from <http://jjie.org/teens->

Dadzie, P. S. (2008) Reading for Education: The Roles of Libraries. *Ghana Library Journal* Vol. 20. No. 1. pp. 1- 14.

Adu-Sarkodee, R., Asante, E., & Akussah, M. (2015). Relationship between uses of social media on reading habits: Evidence from senior high students in Ghana. *Information and Knowledge Management*,5(11), 26-32.

